

Non-isothermal decomposition kinetics of bayeritic bauxite

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Abstract : Kinetics of thermal decomposition of bauxite sample has been studied by thermogravimetric analysis (TG-DTGA) in static air under non-isothermal condition. Integral approximation method of Coats and Redfern was used to determine the kinetic parameters like order of reaction and activation energy for the dehydration process. Different kinetic functions were also derived with the experimental data applying Jerez method to ascertain the decomposition mechanism of bauxite. It has been observed that the dehydration reaction followed first order reaction kinetics with contracting volume kinetic mechanism where mass transfer by diffusion between parent bauxite and dehydrated pseudo boehmite phases determines the rate of dehydration.

Keywords : Bauxite, non-isothermal decomposition, thermogravimetry, activation energy, kinetic parameters.

Introduction

The most important hydrated alumina mineral, rich in alumina, is bauxite which is principally composed of one or more hydrated aluminum mineral phases like gibbsite (γ Al(OH)₃), boehmite (γ Al-O-OH), diaspore (α Al-O-OH), and tohdite (HAl₅O₈) with impurities like quartz, goethite (FeO(OH)), haematite (Fe₂O₃), anatase (TiO₂) and minor amount alkaline-earth oxides etc. The crystal sheet of aluminium monohydrate is orthorhombic while that of aluminium trihydrate is monoclinic and water plays a vital role in the structure formation. The bauxite is widely used as starting materials for the synthesis of technical alumina by Bayer's process suitable for the manufacture of electrical insulators, abrasives, technical porcelain, refractories, catalyst carriers, engineering components, membranes, grinding media, substrates for electronic industry, apart from major source of metallurgical alumina for the extraction of metallic aluminium. When bauxite is heat treated, dehydration reaction takes place with gradual expulsion of the water molecules through the intermediate formation of several metastable transition phases [Chi (χ), Eta (η), Gamma (γ), Delta (Δ), Iota (ι) Theta (θ), Kappa (κ) and Beta (β) etc.] with progressive variation in crystallographic nature, specific surface

area and grain morphology until most stable form of alumina, corundum (α -Al₂O₃) is obtained¹⁻³. A thorough understanding of the dehydration kinetics can be highly useful to evaluate the reaction mechanism which is significantly important in controlling the course of reaction, quality of the product and optimisation of the process parameters. Many research workers⁴⁻⁶ extensively studied the isothermal transformation kinetics of gibbsite, boehmite and bayerite to corundum via series of transition aluminas. Most of these methods involve force fitting of thermal analysis data to a simple kinetic model and consider the pre-exponential factor as independent of temperature. In contrast, dehydration kinetics and transformation mechanism of bauxite minerals which is basically a solid solution of gibbsite and diaspore, remain still uncertain under a non-isothermal condition. Compared to conventional isothermal studies, non-isothermal methods for determining kinetic parameters have several advantages. A single sample and fewer data are required and the kinetics can be calculated over an entire temperature range in a continuous manner. But a particular disadvantage of the non-isothermal data method, compared to the isothermal one, is the uncertainty over the reaction mechanism. Moreover, conventional methods⁷⁻¹³ used for the kinetic analysis results in ambiguity under linear heating

conditions, especially if the studied reaction follows a diffusion-controlled kinetic law. Therefore, the systematic study on the thermal decomposition and the kinetic properties of bauxite mineral may provide a deep insight into the effect of thermal treatment on the structural changes and elucidate the actual mechanism of decomposition of the bauxite employing non-isothermal thermogravimetric analysis.

In the present work, the reliability, validity and accuracy of model free Coats and Redfern¹⁴ integral approximation method to determine the kinetic model and kinetic parameters on the thermal decomposition of natural bauxite sample from its non-isothermal TG-DTGA data are being examined and compared with the kinetic functions computed from the differential method of Jerez¹⁵.

Rate equations :

The solid state fractional decomposition of bauxite sample (α) ($0 < \alpha < 1$) under non-isothermal condition can be expressed in terms of weight change in the following way,

$$\alpha = \frac{W_0 - W}{W_0 - W_\infty} \quad (1)$$

Where, W_0 , W and W_∞ are the initial weight, weight at any instant during thermal analysis and final weight of the sample respectively.

The decomposition reaction based on the n -th order reaction kinetics can be written as :

$$-d\alpha/dt = k (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (2)$$

i.e. the rate of reaction is proportional to n -th power of undecomposed part of the sample, n the order of the reaction, k the specific reaction rate constant.

The rate constant which is a function of temperature can be expressed by Arrhenius equation,

$$k = A e^{-E/RT} \quad (3)$$

Where, E the activation energy of the reaction, A the pre-exponential factor, R the gas constant, T the temperature in absolute scale.

Substituting k from eq. (3) into the eq. (2) gives

$$-d\alpha/dt = A e^{-E/RT} (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (4)$$

After separating variables, eq. (4) becomes

$$-d\alpha/(1 - \alpha)^n = A e^{-E/RT} dt \quad (5)$$

Again,

$$\text{the rate of heating } \beta = dT/dt \text{ or, } dt = dT/\beta \quad (6)$$

The integral approach is generally believed to be more convenient, reliable and accurate than differential method¹⁶.

Putting the expression of dt in eq. (5) and integrating between temperature limits T_1 and T_2 and fractional decomposition α (increasing from 0 to 1 of the solid reactant during course of reaction), the following equation is obtained.

$$-\int_0^\infty \frac{d\alpha}{(1 - \alpha)^n} = \frac{A}{\beta} \int_{T_1}^{T_2} e^{-E/RT} dT \quad (7)$$

But the integration at the right hand side $\frac{A}{\beta} \int_{T_1}^{T_2} e^{-E/RT} dT$

has no analytical solution. Therefore, the solution advanced by Coats and Redfern is used to determine the kinetic parameters of the dehydration reaction. The approximate solution as given by Coats and Redfern method is as follows,

$$\ln \left[-\ln \frac{(1 - \alpha)}{T^2} \right] = \ln \frac{AR}{\beta E} \left[\left(1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right) \right] - \frac{E}{RT} \quad (8)$$

(for $n = 1$)
and

$$\ln \left[-\ln \left\{ \frac{-1(1 - \alpha)^{1-n}}{(1 - n)T^2} \right\} \right] = \ln \frac{AR}{\beta E} \left[\left(1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right) \right] - \frac{E}{RT} \quad (\text{for } n \neq 1) \quad (9)$$

If it is assumed that the expression $\ln \frac{AR}{\beta E} \left[\left(1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right) \right]$

remains constant over the temperature range of decomposition, then the eqs. (8) and (9) assumes a linear form, then a plot of $\ln [-\ln (1 - \alpha)/T^2]$ vs $1/T$ for $n = 1$ and $\ln [-\ln \{1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1-n}\}/(1 - n)T^2]$ vs $1/T$ for $n \neq 1$ gives the value of E from the slope ($-E/R$) and the value of A

from the intercept $\ln \frac{AR}{\beta E} \left[\left(1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right) \right]$.

To determine the exact mechanism of decomposition reaction, the method proposed by Jerez *et al.*¹⁵ is used.

The rate of reaction of a thermal decomposition of solids can be expressed by the following general equation :

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A e^{-E/RT} f(\alpha) \quad (10)$$

Where $f(\alpha)$ is a function which depends on the actual reaction mechanism. When the temperature of the sample is increased at a constant rate,

$$\beta = \frac{dT}{dt}$$

Hence, eq. (10) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dT} = \frac{A}{\beta} e^{-E/RT} f(\alpha) \quad (11)$$

By differentiating the logarithmic form of eq. (11) with respect to $d \{ \ln (1 - \alpha) \}$ we obtain,

$$\frac{d \left(\ln \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dT} \right) \right)}{d \left(\ln (1 - \alpha) \right)} = - \frac{E}{R} \frac{d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}{d \left(\ln (1 - \alpha) \right)} + \frac{d \left(\ln f(\alpha) \right)}{d \left(\ln (1 - \alpha) \right)} \quad (12)$$

or,

$$\frac{\Delta \left(\ln \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dT} \right) \right)}{\Delta \left(\ln (1 - \alpha) \right)} = - \frac{E}{R} \frac{\Delta \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}{\Delta \left(\ln (1 - \alpha) \right)} + \frac{\Delta \left(\ln f(\alpha) \right)}{\Delta \left(\ln (1 - \alpha) \right)} \quad (13)$$

Hence,

$$\frac{\Delta \left(\ln \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dT} \right) \right) - \Delta \left(\ln f(\alpha) \right)}{\Delta \left(\ln (1 - \alpha) \right)} = - \frac{E}{R} \frac{\Delta \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}{\Delta \left(\ln (1 - \alpha) \right)} \quad (14)$$

The classification of kinetic models based on $f(\alpha)$ values [eq. (14)] to determine the reaction mechanism for solid state decomposition reaction can be found out as per Table 1.

Thus, the plots of the left-hand side of eq. (14) against $\Delta (1/T)/\Delta \left(\ln (1 - \alpha) \right)$ should be a straight line with a

Table 1. Classification of kinetic models for reaction mechanism¹⁵

Kinetic classification	$f(\alpha)$
(1) Sigmoidal α - t curves	
Avrami-Erofeev (A_2)	$2(1 - \alpha)[- \ln (1 - \alpha)]^{1/2}$
Avrami-Erofeev (A_3)	$3(1 - \alpha)[- \ln (1 - \alpha)]^{2/3}$
Avrami-Erofeev (A_4)	$4(1 - \alpha)[- \ln (1 - \alpha)]^{3/4}$
Prout-Tompkins (B_1)	$\alpha(1 - \alpha)$
(2) Acceleratory α - t curves	
Power law (P_1)	$n\alpha^{(n-1)/n}$
Exponential law (E_1)	α
(3) Deceleratory α - t curves	
(3.1) Based on geometrical models	
Contracting area (R_2)	$2(1 - \alpha)^{1/2}$
Contracting volume (R_3)	$2(1 - \alpha)^{1/3}$
(3.2) Based on diffusion mechanism	
One dimensional (D_1)	α^{-1}
Two dimensional (D_2)	$[- \ln(1 - \alpha)]^{-1}$
Three dimensional (D_3)	$2/3(1 - \alpha)^{2/3}[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/3}]^{-1}$
(3.3) Based on "order" of reaction	
First order (F_1)	$(1 - \alpha)$
Second order (F_2)	$(1 - \alpha)^2$
Third order (F_3)	$1/2(1 - \alpha)^3$

slope of $-E/R$, irrespective of the $f(\alpha)$ employed. However, we can select the particular $f(\alpha)$ that fits best the actual mechanism of the studied reaction by means of correlation coefficient and intercept values which in an ideal agreement with eq. (14) should be one and zero respectively. The value of the $f(\alpha)$ is being calculated from α_{\max} i.e. the maximum fractional decomposition.

Experimental

Naturally occurring bauxite sample of Sourastra (India) has been chosen as starting material for the study.

The bulk sample is first ground to fine powder, dried at 110 °C and stored in a dessicator. The finely agated sample is chemically analyzed with respect to chemical constituent following standard procedure. It is then characterized in terms of specific surface area and particle size distribution in Strohlen Area Meter II apparatus from low temperature N₂ adsorption data using BET principle and Malvern Zetasizer (Model ZEN-1600) instrument in the range 0.06–6.0 micrometer respectively. The FTIR spectrogram of bauxite powder is recorded in a Perkin-Elmer-783 instrument in KBr phase in the range 400–4000 cm⁻¹. The identification of the crystalline phases of

as received bauxite sample and calcined at 300 °C and 500 °C are carried out in a Phillips automatic X-ray diffractometer (X'Pert PRO PW-3071) using Ni filtered Cu-K α radiation of 1.5405 Å at a scanning rate of 2°/min. The microstructure of bauxite powder is studied by scanning electron microscope (Quanta200, FEI make, Holand). The kinetic study of the decomposition process is performed by differential thermogravimetric analysis. The dynamic thermogravimetric analysis of the sample is carried out using a high temperature Netzsch simultaneous thermal analyser (Model-409) at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ upto 1200 °C. The bauxite sample is taken in the form of loose powder for thermal analysis and pure α -alumina powder is used as reference sample. Afterwards, the kinetic parameters of decomposition are calculated from DTGA data of bauxite following model free integral approach of Coats and Redfern and differential approach of Jerez respectively.

Results and discussion

The physicochemical properties of bauxite sample are

Table 2. Physicochemical characteristics of bauxite sample

Chemical constituent	Amount (w/w%)
Al ₂ O ₃	60.95
SiO ₂	1.42
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.95
TiO ₂	0.65
CaO	2.33
Alkali	0.33
LOI	32.30
Physical properties	
Mean particle size (µm)	1.10
Surface area (m ² /g)	22.17
FTIR spectra (cm ⁻¹)	751, 740, 707, 1036, 3239–3600
Crystalline phases	
Major	Bayerite, bauxite and boehmite
Minor	Quartz and anatase
DTGA peaks (°C)	297.9, 515 (endo)

presented in the Table 2. The typical chemical analysis of bauxite sample indicates that the alumina is the main constituent with low content of silica, iron oxide, calcium oxide and titania as impurities. The bauxite powder also possesses considerably high surface area with microfine particle size distribution. The appearance of broad FTIR absorption spectra (Fig. 1) in the range 3239–3600 cm⁻¹

are associated with stretching vibration of Al-OH groups and the inter-layered water indicating OH groups tetrahedrally coordinated with Al³⁺ ions in bauxite. The -Al=O vibration is visible at 1036 cm⁻¹.

Intense FTIR absorption bands at 751, 740 and 707 cm⁻¹ are assigned to the six coordinated Al³⁺ ions in the molecule. The powder XRD pattern of natural bauxite sample (Fig. 2) confirms the presence of bayerite, bauxite and boehmite as the major mineral phases along with quartz and anatase as minor phases. The product on heat-treatment just above dehydration temperature (300 °C) loses all its original peaks of bauxite and bayerite, leading to transformation into disordered boehmite and pseudo boehmite phases above 500 °C. In bauxite, the oxygen ions are arranged in hexagonal close packed system around Al³⁺ ions. Hence, it is apparent that isostructural similarity between bauxite and boehmite leads to topotactic transformation from bauxite to boehmite and pseudo boehmite on thermal treatment. The SEM micrograph of the bauxite sample (Fig. 3) reveals the elongated microstructure with grain size distribution in the nano range 102–250 nm. The thermal behavior of hydrated alumina depends greatly on the mineral phase composition, the impurity content and the crystallinity of the sample. The TG-DTGA curve of natural bauxite is shown in Fig. 4. The DTGA curve shows a sharp endothermic peak in the range 250–350 °C due to dehydration of hydrated alumina followed by a small endotherm at 515 °C due to dehydroxylation of the boehmite phase. The TGA curve exhibits a total mass loss of 32.60% in the temperature range which is in close agreement with the theoretical value of 34.61% for the decomposition reactions of aluminium trihydrate leading to the initial formation of boehmite, pseudo boehmite or metastable transition aluminas finally to α -alumina¹ with expulsion of structural water at elevated temperatures (300–1200 °C). However, the TGA curve exhibits an evident mass loss of 29.65% in the range 250–550 °C attributing to the following decomposition reaction.

Overall reaction :

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of bauxite sample.

Fig. 2. Powder XRD pattern of bauxite sample.

Fig. 3. Secondary electron image of bayeritic bauxite sample.

Alteration of bauxite by thermal activation with the increase of temperature can be defined as deformation. The differential mass loss with increase of temperature at a constant rate is obtained from the DTGA data. The ratio of the mass loss to the total mass loss after heating to 1200 °C is defined as the mass loss ratio represented by α . The variation in α as a function of temperature is shown in Fig. 5. At first, the kinetic parameters are calculated from DTGA data using model free approach of Coats and Redfern.

Fig. 4. TG-DTG analysis of bayeritic bauxite sample.

Fig. 5. Variation of fractional loss (α) of bayeritic bauxite sample with heat-treated temperature.

The plot of eq. (9) is carried out using Curve Experts software for different values of n . The corresponding correlation coefficient and the standard error of the linear plots are determined and the results are shown in Table 3.

The ' n ' value which yields the maximum correlation coefficient and the minimum standard error is being selected as the order of the decomposition reaction. From the Figs. 6-7 and Table 3, highest correlation coefficient and lowest standard error are achieved corresponding to the n value equal to 1.00 for the non-isothermal decom-

position of the bayeritic bauxite sample, thereby establishing first order dehydration kinetics operating on the studied sample. From the slope of the curve (Fig. 6) for $n = 1.0$, the activation energy of the thermal decomposition reaction is determined as 62.31 kJ/mol employing Coats and Redfern model. It is interesting to note that activation energy obtained for non-isothermal decomposition of the bayeritic bauxite sample is consistent and in close proximity with values 66.5 kJ/mol for gibbsitic bauxite¹⁷ and 69.63 kJ/mol for gibbsite¹⁸ under non-isothermal condition. The slight difference of activation energy

Fig. 6. Plot of $\ln [-\ln ((1 - \alpha)/T^2)]$ vs $1/T$ for Sourastra bayeritic bauxite according to Coats and Redfern equation.

Fig. 7. Plot of $\ln [-\ln \{1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1-n}/(1-n)T^2\}]$ vs $1/T$ for bayeritic bauxite sample according to Coats and Redfern equation.

value for the bayeritic bauxite decomposition from gibbsite under non-isothermal condition may be due to variation of mineralogical composition and associated water layers, disordered crystallinity, stacking faults and precise position of impurity ions in hydrated alumina lattice of

bayeritic bauxite. The kinetic results depicts that the non-isothermal decomposition of bayeritic bauxite involves a complex physical and chemical events and proceeds primarily by means of an interfacial reaction accomplished in a continuous manner.

Table 3. Variation in correlation coefficient and standard error with different n values of bayeritic bauxite sample according to Coats and Redfern model¹⁴

n	Correlation coefficient	Standard error
0.70	0.9900	0.7425
0.75	0.9897	0.7668
0.80	0.9894	0.7987
0.85	0.9889	0.8432
0.90	0.9880	0.9111
0.95	0.9863	1.0380
0.98	0.9839	1.2220
1.00	0.9947	0.3620
1.02	0.9842	1.2110
1.05	0.9870	1.0143
1.10	0.9891	0.8679

Furthermore, from the plot of eq. (14) based on Jerez differential model different kinetic functions are determined and listed in Table 4. Jerez differential model shows a linear trend with maximum correlation coefficient 0.8993 and minimum standard error 0.6091 which elucidates the progressive contracting volume mechanism of the reactant particles. However, the activation energy determined from the slope of the plot is just 48.90 kJ/mol which is on the lower side than that determined for the bauxite sample using model-free integral approach of Coats and Redfern. The less proximity of correlation coefficient and higher standard error to their ideal values for the non-isothermal decomposition study of bauxite following Jerez differen-

Table 4. Correlation coefficient and standard error for different kinetic functions during the thermal decomposition of bayeritic bauxite according to Jerez model¹⁵

Kinetic function	Correlation coefficient	Standard error
Avrami-Erofeev (A_2)	0.8638	0.6634
Avrami-Erofeev (A_3)	0.8665	0.7744
Avrami-Erofeev (A_4)	0.8659	0.6334
Prout-Tompkins (B_1)	0.7144	0.9329
Exponential law (E_1)	0.6962	0.8382
Contracting area (R_2)	0.8638	0.6680
Contracting volume (R_3)	0.8993	0.6091
One dimensional (D_1)	0.7059	1.3260
Two dimensional (D_2)	0.7161	1.3760
Three dimensional (D_3)	0.7216	1.1810
First order (1 : 1)	0.7386	0.8530
Second order (1 : 2)	0.8206	0.9374
Third order (1 : 3)	0.7851	1.1726

tial model demonstrates a certain degree of inaccuracy, thereby suggesting less applicability of this model.

The non-isothermal decomposition of the bayeritic bauxite is, therefore, regarded as interface controlled with progressively contracting volume of the starting reactant particles where mass transfer through dynamic interface between undecomposed bauxite and formed boehmite is the rate controlling process. Thus, it is evident that Coats-Redfern integral model holds good and more reliable than Jerez differential model for evaluating the kinetic parameters of thermal decomposition of the bayeritic bauxite under non-isothermal condition.

References

1. G. Pokol, G. Várhegyi and I. Várady, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1984, **76**, 237.
2. Theo J. Klopogge, D. Huada Ruan and L. Ray Frost, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 2002, **37**, 1121.
3. Joaquín Aguilar-Santillán, Heberto Balmori-Ramírez and Richard C. Uradt, *Int. J. Ceram. Pros. Res.*, 2004, **5**, 196.
4. C. Eyraud and R. Goton, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1954, **51**, 430.
5. G. W. Brindley and M. Nakahira, *Z. Krist.*, 1959, **112**, 136.
6. V. I. Lopushan, G. F. Kuznetsov, R. N. Pletnev and D. G. Kleshev, *Refract. Ind. Ceram.*, 2007, **48**, 378.
7. Haoqun Li, Tianmin Hao, Desheng Li and Darong Chen, *Thermochim. Acta*, 2005, **427**, 9.
8. Takeshi Tsuchida, Ryusaburo Furuichi and Tadao Ishii, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1980, **39**, 103.
9. Haipeng Wang, Bingan Xu, Peter Smith, Michael Davies, Lynette DeSilva and Christine Wingate, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*, 2006, **67**, 2567.
10. Yang Hua-ming, Hu Yue-hua, Yang Wu-guo, Ao Wei-qin and Oiu Guan-Zhou, *J. Cent. South. Univ. Technol.*, 2004, **11**, 173.
11. Z. D. Zivkovic and B. Dobovisck, *J. Thermal. Anal.*, 1977, **12**, 207.
12. B. Zhu, B. Fang and X. Li, *Ceram. Int.*, 2010, **36**, 2493.
13. S. Maitra and B. K. Dutta, *Ind. Chem. Engineer*, 2008, **50**, 337.
14. A. W. Coats and J. P. Redfern, *Nature*, 1964, **201**, 68.
15. A. Jerez, E. Ramos, M. Gaitan, M. L. Veiga and C. Pico, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1987, **115**, 175.
16. P. Budrugaee, D. Homentcovschi and E. Segal, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1997, **300**, 83.
17. L. Rozic, T. Novakovic, N. Jovanovc, A. T. Baricevc and Z. Grabavcic, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **66**, 273.
18. S. K. Mehta and A. Kalsotra, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.*, 1991, **367**, 267.